

STUDIES ON THE CHEMISTRY OF RHENIUM. PART II. COMPLEX
COMPOUNDS OF QUADRIVALENT RHENIUM WITH GALLIC ACID

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Like oxalic acid (cf. Part I) gallic acid has also been found to combine with quadrivalent rhenium to give rise to a complex acid, which has the composition $H_2[(H_2O)_2 \cdot Re(C_6H_2O_2 \cdot OH \cdot COO)_2] \cdot 6H_2O$. The dissociation constants, k_1 and k_2 of the acid, as determined by potentiometric titration, are given by the values 7.1×10^{-5} and 4.4×10^{-7} respectively. A number of alkali, alkaline earth and heavy metal salts of the acid have been described. The sodium salt of the acid like the corresponding rhenioxalate has been found to be diamagnetic.

The complex compounds of quadrivalent rhenium with oxalic acid have been described in the previous paper (this issue p. 171). A complex acid of similar type has now been prepared by the action of gallic acid on pure recrystallised potassium rhenichloride. Its composition may be represented by the formula $H_2[Re \cdot (H_2O)_2 \cdot (C_6H_2O_2 \cdot OH \cdot COO)_2] \cdot 6H_2O$. Of the six water molecules four can easily be removed at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$. The alkali salts, even when dried at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$, have the composition represented by $M_2 [Re (H_2O)_2 \cdot (C_6H_2O_2 \cdot OH \cdot COO)_2]$.

Molecular conductance at infinite dilution of the sodium salt was found to be about 220 ohms⁻¹. This is in agreement with the molar conductance of the uni-bivalent electrolyte.

A series of salts, such as those of sodium, potassium, barium, calcium, lead, thallium, etc., was prepared and studied. The alkali salts are soluble in water, but those of alkaline earth, lead and thallium are insoluble.

Potentiometric titration of the acid with alkali shows that the acid is a dibasic one. The dissociation constants k_1 and k_2 of the acid are 7.1×10^{-5} and 4.4×10^{-7} respectively (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*). The first inflexion of the curve was not obtained, as the values of k_1 and k_2 do not differ much. The complex rhenigallic acid appears to be as strong as the gallic acid itself. ($k = 4.8 \times 10^{-5}$; Ostwald, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1889, 3, 252).

Like the rhenioxalate complexes, sodium rhenigallate has also been found to show a diamagnetic susceptibility, indicating the presence of metallic bonds between rhenium atoms in a dimeric formula.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diaquo-rhenigallic Acid.—Crude potassium rhenichloride was recrystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid. The pure product (1 M) was mixed with gallic acid (4 M, Merck's reagent) in a little water. The mixture was refluxed in a small R.B. flask for about an hour, when a dark brown solution was obtained. This was cooled, filtered and evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid. The residue was extracted with absolute alcohol to remove potassium chloride. This was filtered and the alcoholic solution again evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.

The substance forms deep brown crystals, which reacts acidic in solution. It is highly soluble in water and alcohol; but once dried, it goes very slowly into solution. The substance is quite stable in acid medium, but slowly oxidises in the presence of alkalis.

For analysis, the substance was decomposed with alkali and hydrogen peroxide. From the solution rhenium was estimated as nitron perrhenate.

Carbon and hydrogen were estimated in a semi-micro combustion system.

{ Found : Re, 27.94 ; C, 25.19 ; H, 3.58 ; H₂O (by dehydration at 110°-115°), 11.03. H₂[Re.(H₂O)₂.(C₆H₂O₂.OH.CO₂)₂]. 6H₂O requires Re, 27.93 ; C, 25.22 ; H, 3.60 ; H₂O, 16.22 per cent].

Thus only a part of the water was removed by drying at 110°-115°. {Found (for the product dried at 110-115°): Re, 31.30; C, 28.31; H, 2.66. H₂ [Re. (H₂O)₂. (C₆H₂O₂.OH.CO₂)₂]. 2H₂O requires Re, 31.31; C, 28.28; H, 2.70 per cent].

Potentiometric titration of the acid.—The acid was titrated against alkali potentiometrically. (cf. Figs. 1 and 2)

TABLE I

Alkali soln. = 0.4645M.		Acid soln. = 0.0075M. t = 25°.			
Alkali added.	Molar conc. of alkali.	p _H	k ₁ .	k ₂ .	\bar{n} .
0 c.c.	—	2.88	3.550	—	1.82
0.4	0.1858 × 10 ⁻²	3.65	4.065	—	1.72
0.8	0.3716	4.15	4.135	—	1.49
1.2	0.5574	4.63	4.182	—	1.25
1.6	0.7432	5.16	3.074	—	1.01
2.0	0.9290	5.72	—	6.224	0.76
2.4	1.1148	6.32	—	6.344	0.52
2.8	1.3524	7.30	—	6.689	0.20
3.2	1.4804	8.68	—	6.846	0.016
4.0	—	10.25	—	—	—

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

From Fig. 2 $pK_1 = 4.15$; $k_1 = 7.1 \times 10^{-5}$
 $pK_2 = 6.36$; $k_2 = 4.4 \times 10^{-7}$

Sodium Salt of the Diaquo-rhenigallic Acid.—A concentrated solution of sodium acetate in rectified spirit was added with constant stirring to an alcoholic solution of the complex acid. The sodium salt separating was allowed to stand for a while with frequent shaking. This was filtered and treated with a concentrated solution of sodium acetate in alcohol. The product was then filtered, washed thoroughly at first with rectified spirit and then with alcohol. Finally, it was dried in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.

The substance forms a light brown crystalline powder. It is highly soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents. The substance is quite stable in acid, but is rapidly oxidised in presence of alkali. Its aqueous solution reacts alkaline. {Found : Re, 30.90 ; C, 27.92 ;

H, 1.62; Na, 7.64. $\text{Na}_2[\text{Re}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{OH.COO})_2]$ requires Re, 30.90; C, 27.91; H, 1.66; Na, 7.64 per cent.

On drying at $110^\circ\text{--}115^\circ$ the substance remained unchanged.

For analysis, the substance was decomposed with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide and rhenium was separated as Re_2S_7 . In the filtrate sodium was estimated as Na_2SO_4 . Rhenium was estimated as nitron perrhenate after oxidation of the sulphide to perrhenate.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured in a Gouy's balance. $\chi_g = -0.00863 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = -4.391 \times 10^{-6}$.

Equivalent conductance.

							$t = 25^\circ$.								
Dilution (litres) ..	32	64	128	256	512	1024									
Δv ..	58.2	72.9	79.5	87.3	98.2	109.0									

Mol. conductance = 220 ohms⁻¹ approx.

Potassium Salt.—An alcoholic solution of potassium acetate was added dropwise to a similar solution of rhenigallic acid. The potassium salt separating as a brown powder was filtered and again digested with an alcoholic solution of potassium acetate. The mixture was allowed to stand for a while and then filtered. The product was washed and dried as usual. The substance is highly soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents.

Potassium was estimated as potassium sulphate after removal of rhenium as in the previous case. {Found: Re, 29.32; C, 26.44; H, 1.59; K, 12.26. $\text{K}_2[\text{Re}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{OH.COO})_2]$ requires Re, 29.33; C, 26.50; H, 1.58 K, 12.30; per cent.}

Ammonium salt was prepared exactly in the same manner as the potassium salt. The substance forms a brown crystalline powder and resembles the alkali salts in properties. Ammonia was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. {Found: Re, 31.30; NH_4 , 6.08. $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Re}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{OH.COO})_2]$ requires Re, 31.31; NH_4 , 6.06 per cent.}

Thallium Salt.—An aqueous solution of the thalious sulphate was added dropwise to that of the sodium salt of the rhenigallic acid. The insoluble thallium salt separating as a brown precipitate was washed and dried as usual.

The substance is insoluble in water and organic solvents, but soluble in dilute mineral acids.

For analysis, the substance was decomposed with alkaline hydrogen peroxide and from the acidified solution rhenium was precipitated as Re_2S_7 . From the filtrate thallium was precipitated as Tl_2S in alkaline medium. This was dissolved and estimated as thalious chromate. {Found: Re, 19.25; Tl, 42.22. $\text{Tl}_2[\text{Re}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{OH.COO})_2]$ requires Re, 19.29; Tl, 42.32 per cent.}

Barium Salt.—A solution of barium chloride was added drop by drop to that of the sodium salt of the complex acid. The barium salt that separated out, was washed and dried as in the other cases. The substance is insoluble in water and organic solvents, but readily soluble in dilute mineral acids.

For analysis, the substance was treated with alkaline hydrogen peroxide and from the acidified solution barium was precipitated and estimated as BaSO_4 . From the filtrate rhenium was precipitated as Re_2S_7 and then oxidised and estimated as usual. {Found: Re, 24.33; Ba, 17.87. $\text{Ba}[\text{Re}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{OH.COO})_2]$ requires Re, 24.32; Ba, 17.91 per cent.}

Calcium Salt.—This was prepared from an aqueous solution of calcium chloride and that of the sodium salt of the complex acid. The brown precipitate of the calcium salt was washed and dried as in the previous cases.

The substance was decomposed with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide; and from the acidified solution rhenium was separated as Re_2S_7 . From the filtrate calcium was estimated as CaSO_4 after evaporation and heating with sulphuric acid. {Found: Re, 29.41; Ca, 6.30. $\text{Ca}[\text{Re} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot (\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2) \text{OH} \cdot \text{COO}]_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Re, 29.43; Ca, 6.33 per cent.}

Lead salt was obtained as a brown crystalline precipitate from an aqueous solution of the lead acetate and that of the sodium salt of the complex acid. The product was washed and dried as in all other cases.

Lead was estimated as lead sulphate following the procedure described under barium salt. {Found: Re, 23.51; Pb, 26.16. $\text{Pb}[\text{Re} \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot (\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2 \cdot \text{OH} \cdot \text{COO})_2] \cdot 1.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Re, 23.54; Pb, 26.20 per cent.}

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